

AI applications in Initial Teacher Education: A systematic mapping review

Abstract

The landscape of education is undergoing rapid transformation, with increasing interest in the use of artificial intelligence (AI) for teaching and learning. Given the growing recognition that AI literacy and skills are essential for the future, understanding how initial teacher education (ITE) has been preparing pre-service teachers (PSTs) is particularly crucial. This systematic mapping review explores the scope and nature of research on AI applications in ITE, synthesising 138 primary studies indexed in the Web of Science, Scopus, EBSCOhost, ERIC, ProQuest and Google Scholar, or captured through snowballing in OpenAlex. Studies were included if they explored AI uses in ITE within a formal learning setting, published in English between 2014 and 2024, and were empirical journal articles or conference papers. The findings reveal a growing interest in adaptive systems, including generative AI, and stress a need to build PST AI confidence and problem-solving through real-world tasks, including a focus on ethics and data privacy.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence, pre-service teacher education, adaptive systems, generative AI, AI literacy

Authors

Melissa Bond¹, Emily Oxley², Lydia Lymperis³

Please cite as:

Bond, M., Oxley, E., & Lymperis, L. (2024). AI applications in Initial Teacher Education: A systematic mapping review. *Zenodo pre-print*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880128>

Under consideration for publication in the forthcoming book 'Handbook on Artificial Intelligence and Higher Education'.

¹ EPPI Centre, University College London, UK

Knowledge Center for Education, University of Stavanger, Norway
National Institute of Teaching, UK

² School of Social and Environmental Sustainability, University of Glasgow, UK

³ Faculty of Education, University of Cambridge, UK
National Institute of Teaching, UK

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has come a long way since its initial development in the 1960s. What began as fringe, experimental technology supporting attempts to mechanise human intelligence (Cordeschi, 2007), has now blossomed into a dynamic field with the potential to revolutionise education. Initially confined to the periphery of educational research, AI has steadily moved into the mainstream, evolving from a niche interest to a pivotal area of study and application (e.g., UNESCO, 2024a). Although a universally accepted definition of AI remains elusive, Baker & Smith (2019) describe it as systems capable of performing “cognitive tasks, usually associated with human minds, particularly learning and problem-solving.” (p. 10). This includes tasks such as learning from experience, adapting to new situations, understanding natural language, and solving complex problems. In that sense, AI spans a broad spectrum of technologies and methodologies designed to simulate or extend human cognitive abilities. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) developed a typology that categorises AI higher education research and applications into four broad domains: Profiling and prediction, Intelligent tutoring systems, Assessment and evaluation, and Adaptive systems and personalisation, providing a structured lens through which to examine how AI is influencing various facets of education. This typology has since been used and updated in a meta review of 66 evidence syntheses (Bond et al., 2024; see Figure 1).

Arguably, the transformative potential of AI in education (AIEd) lies in its capacity to inform the design of novel approaches to address many long-standing challenges in the field, including achievement gaps and teacher development, retention, and shortages (Luckin et al., 2016). For instance, AI-driven learning analytics can provide real-time insights into student performance, empowering educators to tailor their teaching strategies to individual needs and significantly enhance personalised learning experiences (Gedrimiene et al., 2024; Ouyang & Zhang, 2024; Vashishth, 2024). Furthermore, AI-powered predictive analytics hold the promise of increased retention rates by helping educators identify students at risk of dropping out and allowing for timely interventions (Dwivedi et al., 2024; Sihare, 2024). Intelligent tutoring systems take this a step further by making it possible to provide bespoke instruction and feedback, which could revolutionise how students engage with educational content (Lampropoulos, 2023; Lin et al., 2023; Mousavinasab et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Adapted AIEd typology (Bond et al., 2024), adapted from Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019).

AI can also play a crucial role in automating assessment and evaluation processes, offering immediate feedback and more consistent grading standards (Cope et al., 2020; García-Gorrostieta et al., 2018; González-Calatayud et al., 2021). Additionally, the integration of natural language processing (NLP) within AI systems opens up exciting new possibilities for analysing textual and oral discourse. For example, automated essay grading (AEG) employs machine learning algorithms to evaluate written responses to open-ended questions, which can offer deeper insights into student learning and provide more targeted support (Alqahtani et al., 2023; Shaik, 2022). Adding to this transformative potential, recent developments in generative AI (genAI) tools—such as ChatGPT and DALL-E—mark a significant leap forward. These technologies go beyond just enhancing traditional educational tools by paving the way for entirely new forms of educational interaction. ChatGPT, for instance, offers the potential to facilitate dynamic learning environments by engaging students in conversational learning and providing instant feedback, thus expanding the boundaries of traditional teaching methods (Bozkurt & Sharma, 2023; Bozkurt et al., 2023).

Despite these advancements, more research is still needed to fully understand and harness the potential of AI. Addressing challenges such as the ethical use of AI (Holmes et al., 2021), ensuring transparency and explainability of AI systems to maintain algorithmic fairness and prevent reinforcing existing inequalities (Khosravi et al., 2022), and navigating the pedagogical implications of increasingly autonomous AI systems in educational settings (Han et al., 2023) are becoming increasingly important. Moreover, a greater focus on system change is essential: researchers and developers must find ways to work in collaboration with educators in co-

designing AI tools with input from teachers, students, and parents to effectively address the inherent ‘messiness’ of real-world educational environments (Luckin et al., 2016).

Impact of AIEd on Teachers

The growing prominence and impact of AI in education mean that AI is becoming increasingly relevant to initial teacher education (ITE). Pre-service teachers (PSTs) must be prepared for a classroom environment where AI tools are prevalent and integral to the learning process. This is critical to ensuring that teachers can effectively integrate AI into their practice and adapt to the evolving educational landscape (Luckin et al., 2016). This need becomes even more pronounced considering the challenges of integrating technology into educational courses, including AI. Factors such as school culture, resource availability, and teachers’ attitudes, knowledge, and skills often hinder effective technology integration (Farjon et al., 2019; Menabò et al., 2021).

Governments worldwide are increasingly recognising the importance of preparing teachers for the integration of AI into the classroom. In the European Union, the Digital Education Action Plan emphasises integrating digital and AI literacy into teacher training programmes to enhance educators’ ability to use these tools effectively (European Commission, 2020). Similarly, the U.S. Department of Education has called for the inclusion of AI concepts in teacher preparation to ensure that educators can harness AI technologies responsibly and effectively (U.S. Department of Education, 2023). In the United Kingdom, the Department for Education (DfE) has recognised the transformative potential of AI in teaching and learning but also highlights the significant challenges educators face in adapting to the rapidly evolving genAI landscape. Specifically, the DfE’s recent report on genAI highlights educators’ reported difficulties with risk assessments, training, and monitoring the impact of these tools, along with the importance of incorporating genAI literacy into teacher training and development programmes (DfE, 2024). Educators have also called for training in basic digital and AI literacy, ethical genAI use, and aligning genAI with good pedagogical practices (DfE, 2023). In response, the DfE is exploring ways to integrate accredited genAI training into both ITE and ongoing professional development, while ensuring that human teachers remain central to education (DfE, 2023).

Prior AIEd syntheses in higher education and ITE

The growing interest in AI in higher education (AIHed) is highlighted by the significant attention given to previous reviews and evidence syntheses. For instance, Zawacki-Richter et al.’s (2019) review has gained widespread recognition, with over 2,800 citations, reflecting the increasing public interest in this field. Examples of prior AIHed tertiary syntheses are typically embedded within secondary research projects, such as Saghiri et al.’s (2022) analysis of four systematic reviews in their scoping review of AI applications in dental education. The meta-review by Bond et al. (2024) stands out as the first standalone tertiary review of the scope and nature of AIHed research. The authors analysed 66 secondary studies published between 2018 and July 2023, revealing a heavy focus on reviews exploring adaptive systems and personalisation, particularly the use of chatbots, virtual assistants, and personalised content delivery. Moreover, it was found that these insights are predominantly skewed towards research from STEM and Health & Welfare fields, indicating a need for increased attention to

AIEd applications in other disciplines, as well as institutional and administrative applications, which have been relatively neglected in existing research.

Within the context of ITE, current evidence on AI in teacher education highlights various ways in which these technologies can be incorporated into teacher preparation programmes. The synthesis by Salas-Pilco et al. (2022) revealed that machine learning, natural language processing, and vision-based mobile augmented reality, combined with learning analytics, can be used for tasks such as automatically scoring PSTs' video presentations, classifying written reflections, and predicting dropout rates amongst PSTs and identifying at-risk groups based on behaviours such as changes in engagement and interactions. The studies also reported using various software tools, including AI algorithms, online platforms such as Moodle, MOOCs, and data analysis tools such as programming languages and statistical software. These tools supported PSTs' self-study through chatbots for scaling mentoring processes, assessed PSTs' teaching competency via an intelligent assessment system, and automatically detected discourse characteristics from textual data (Salas-Pilco et al., 2022).

Despite the promise shown by these technologies, the practical implementation within ITE curricula is still limited, with many teacher education programmes struggling to integrate these technologies in a meaningful and cohesive way (Langran et al., 2024). The synthesis conducted by Celik et al. (2022) indicates that despite the increase in studies on AI use in teaching, there remains a notable lack of focus on AI's role in PST education. Furthermore, efforts to synthesise research on emerging AI technologies, such as genAI, have remained largely unexplored within the context of ITE, despite burgeoning evidence of their potential to significantly enhance—and even transform—the teaching and learning process (e.g., Montenegro-Rueda et al., 2023; Rudolph et al., 2023), highlighting a significant gap in both research and practice. This systematic mapping review seeks to address these gaps by exploring the current state of AI integration in ITE, building on previous syntheses while introducing new insights on the use of genAI.

Research questions

Against this background, this review seeks to answer the following questions:

1. When, where and by whom has research on AI applications in ITE been published?
2. Where and how has research on AI in ITE been conducted?
3. What applications of AI within ITE have been researched?

Method

In order to map the current state of AI research in ITE, a systematic mapping review was conducted using transparent and rigorous methods (Gough et al., 2012; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020), with the reporting here guided by the PRISMA guidelines (Page et al., 2021) and checked against the QuEST appraisal tool (Bond et al., 2024). All search strategy information and raw data can be found on the OSF (Bond, Oxley, et al., 2024).

Search strategy and study selection

Search string development

A search string was adapted from two previous AI reviews (Bond et al., 2024; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019); the AI terms were augmented with “generative AI” and “ChatGPT”, and initial teacher education terms were identified from an initial scoping search of pertinent literature (see Table 1; Bond, Oxley, et al., 2024).

Table 1. Mapping review search string.

AI	“artificial intelligence” OR “machine intelligence” OR “intelligent support” OR “intelligent virtual reality” OR “chat bot*” OR “chatbot*” OR “machine learning” OR “automated tutor” OR “personal tutor*” OR “intelligent agent*” OR “expert system” OR “neural network” OR “natural language processing” OR “intelligent tutor*” OR “adaptive learning system*” OR “adaptive educational system*” OR “adaptive testing” OR “decision trees” OR “clustering” OR “logistic regression” OR “adaptive system*” OR “generative AI” OR “ChatGPT”
AND	
Initial teacher education	“initial teacher education” OR “pre-service teacher*” OR “preservice teacher” OR “trainee teacher” OR “student teacher*”

Searching

The first search was conducted in April 2024, with subsequent searches conducted until 26 September 2024 to ensure the inclusion of as much extant literature as possible. The platforms and databases searched have been identified as being particularly useful for evidence synthesis (Gusenbauer & Haddaway, 2020), namely the Web of Science, Scopus, EBSCOhost (all databases including ERIC) and ProQuest. Google Scholar was also searched using Publish or Perish software (Harzing, 2007) and the OpenAlex platform (Priem et al., 2022) was searched via the evidence synthesis software EPPI Reviewer (Thomas et al., 2023). The period 2014 – 2024 was used as a filter, in order to map a range of trends in AI use across a decade of research. All search results ($n = 2,173$) were exported as .txt or .ris files and imported into EPPI Reviewer, where duplicates ($n = 571$) were automatically removed (see Figure 2).

Inclusion/exclusion criteria and screening

Prior to beginning the screening process, explicit inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined (see Table 2). Studies were included if they explored the use of AI within formal ITE settings (e.g. within a course or on placement) through primary empirical research and were a journal article or conference paper published after 2014 in English. In order to ensure inter-rater agreement between the reviewers, two authors (MB and EO) screened the same 100 items on title and abstract, achieving almost perfect agreement (Cohen's $\kappa = 0.91$; Landis & Koch, 1977). After the three disagreements were reconciled, priority screening mode was enabled within EPPI Reviewer, and the remaining 1,502 items were screened by the same two reviewers in single screener mode. Priority screening uses machine learning to present items first that it deems the most relevant, compared to previously items that have already been screened. In this case, the algorithm was trained using the exclusion codes ‘EXCLUDE not about ITE’ and ‘EXCLUDE not about AI’, alongside one inclusion code (INCLUDE on title & abstract). After all items were screened on title and abstract, 228 full texts were obtained to be screened on full text. To continue ensuring inter-rater reliability at the screening on full text stage, 20 items

were blind screened by the same two authors, achieving 100% agreement. The same two authors then screened the rest of the items, identifying 138 for data extraction and synthesis.

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Published between 2014-2024	Published before 2014
English language	Research published in languages other than English
AI uses within initial teacher education	Not about the use of AI within ITE
Formal learning setting	AI uses outside of formal ITE courses/practicum
Primary, empirical research	Secondary research (e.g. meta-analysis), theoretical research
Journal articles, conference papers	Book chapters, dissertations, reports, grey literature

Data extraction

The data extracted for this mapping review included publication and authorship characteristics (e.g., publication type, country of all authors), study design (e.g., methodology, number of participants), the role of AI in the study (e.g., intervention, analysis only), and the type of AI (e.g., adaptive learning system, as per the typology in Bond et al. (2024) and Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019)). Policy and practice recommendations, alongside future research recommendations, were also coded inductively, as they emerged from the included studies. All data were manually extracted within EPPI Reviewer, and an initial five studies were coded by all authors to ensure agreement and common understanding of the coding scheme. The rest of the items were then divided between the authors. Please see Bond, Oxley, et al. (2024) for the full data extraction tool.

Data synthesis

A narrative synthesis of the extracted data was undertaken (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006), including narrative descriptions to accompany tables and figures created using Word and Excel throughout the text. In order to provide further visual overviews, interactive evidence and gap maps were produced using the EPPI Mapper application (Digital Solution Foundry & EPPI-Centre, 2023), alongside an openly accessible web database¹ of the included studies, created with EPPI Visualiser (EPPI-Centre, n.d.), where all coding can be viewed.

Figure 2. PRISMA diagram.

Methodological limitations

Whilst this review was conducted as rigorously as possible, some limitations must be acknowledged. Firstly, due to the scope of this project, the decision to limit the time period to the last ten years will mean that a substantial body of important formative literature will not be included in this mapping review. This is also true of any research that has been published in languages other than English or in publications other than journal articles and conference papers. However, we have included pre-prints, in order to take account of emerging research, and conducting future systematic reviews might be considered that widen the scope of this work.

Findings

When, where and by whom has research been undertaken?

General publication characteristics

The 138 studies about AI applications in ITE identified by this review have predominantly been published as journal articles (86.2%, $n = 119$) as opposed to indexed conference papers (13.8%, $n = 19$), with 68.8% ($n = 95$) of all studies available open access. There has been a proliferation of interest in the role that AI can play in initial teacher education over the past two years in particular (see Figure 3), the majority of which appear to be due to the advancements and public availability of genAI, such as ChatGPT (Ansari et al., 2024).

Figure 3. Study distribution 2015 – 2024.

Authorship characteristics

AI in ITE research is almost always conducted collaboratively (84.1%, $n = 116$), with the majority of first authors working in an Education faculty (58.7%, $n = 81$).² The authorship of research has been slightly dominated by researchers in Europe (37.0%, $n = 51$) and Asia (33.3%, $n = 46$), although authors from the USA have been the most productive (18.1%, $n = 25$; see Table 3). Whilst the presence of research from the Middle Eastern (14.5%, $n = 20$) and African authors (10.9%, $n = 15$) is slightly higher than that found in other AI and EdTech reviews (e.g., Bond et al., 2024), only two studies from Oceania (1.4%) and no studies from South American authors were identified in this review.

Geographical characteristics of study contexts

Research has been conducted in 41 different countries (see Figure 4), reflecting a slightly more balanced spread across continents. However, 11 studies (8.0%) did not mention which country the research was being undertaken in, only two studies were undertaken in Oceania (both in Australia; Getenet, 2024; McLeod & Richardson, 2023), and no studies have been undertaken within South America. The top six countries reflect the same authorship patterns, with the USA, China and Germany the most researched contexts (see Table 4).

How has research on AI in ITE been conducted?

Disciplinary focus and topics studied

Mirroring the findings of the AI meta review (Bond et al., 2024), 34 studies (24.6%) did not disclose in which particular subject areas (e.g. foreign language learning) or educational level (e.g. primary school) their research participants were studying to become teachers in. Of those that could be identified, the most researched disciplinary areas were Science (21.7%, $n = 30$), English (15.9%, $n = 22$), primary/elementary education (15.9%, $n = 22$) and Maths (14.5%, $n = 20$), with secondary education (7.2%, $n = 10$), early childhood education (5.1%, $n = 7$) and Social Studies (5.1%, $n = 7$) the next most studied. Studies were also coded inductively for specific topics of focus,³ although this was heavily dominated by research that explored

‘Perceptions/awareness/experiences of AI’ (43.5%, $n = 60$) and/or ‘Intention to use AI/acceptance’ (15.9%, $n = 22$).

Table 3. Top ten most productive countries by author.

Rank	Country	Continent	n	%
1	USA	North America	25	18.1%
2	China	Asia	20	14.5%
3	Germany	Europe	16	11.6%
4	Türkiye	Middle East	15	10.9%
5	South Korea	Asia	12	8.7%
6	South Africa	Africa	11	8.0%
7	UK	Europe	8	5.8%
8	Finland	Europe	7	5.1%
9	Saudi Arabia	Middle East	6	4.3%
=	Spain	Spain	6	4.3%

Figure 4. Geographical location of studies.

Methodological characteristics

The majority of studies used quantitative approaches (57.2%, $n = 79$), as opposed to qualitative (23.9%, $n = 33$) or mixed methods (18.8%, $n = 26$), with surveys the most popular form of data collection (65.9%, $n = 91$), followed by written work (such as reflections, 23.9%, $n = 33$) and semi-structured interviews (18.1%, $n = 25$). There were a small number of studies that collected multimodal data, such as video recordings (6.5%, $n = 9$; e.g., teaching demonstrations, Hwang et al., 2024), physiological data (3.6%, $n = 5$; e.g., Ezquerro et al., 2023), and log data (2.9%, $n = 4$; e.g., Dai et al., 2024), although the combination of data collection methods emerged multiple times as a suggestion for future research (e.g., Mnguni, 2024). The majority of studies involved less than 100 participants (60.9%, $n = 84$), with more than a third of all studies (39.9%, $n = 55$) having less than 50. Many studies involved experiments that lasted less than a day or

were surveys capturing data at one time point, with only 19 studies (13.8%) capturing data across a one semester period.

Table 4. Top twelve countries where studies have been undertaken.

Rank	Country	Continent	<i>n</i>	%
1	USA	North America	17	12.3%
2	China	Asia	16	11.6%
3	Germany	Europe	14	10.1%
4	Türkiye	Middle East	11	8.0%
5	South Korea	Asia	11	8.0%
6	South Africa	Africa	7	5.1%
7	Spain	Europe	6	4.3%
8	Indonesia	Asia	5	3.6%
=	Nigeria	Africa	4	2.9%
=	Slovenia	Europe	4	2.9%
=	Switzerland	Europe	4	2.9%
=	Taiwan	Asia	4	2.9%

Ethical considerations

Only half of all studies included explicit information about participant consent (50.0%, *n* = 69), with a further eight studies (5.8%) that had received ethical approval from their institution's ethical review board but that did not go on to mention how participant consent was obtained. Information about data sharing was also coded, revealing that only five studies (3.6%) have their data openly available online and 41 studies (29.7%) where the author can be contacted. The vast majority of studies did not mention data availability at all (59.4%, *n* = 82).

What applications of AI within ITE have been researched?

Research on ITE has predominantly explored PSTs attitudes towards AI or their intentions to use it (56.5%, *n* = 78), with studies often treating AI as one entity or general idea (24.6% of all studies, *n* = 34), rather than specific types, although studies on PSTs intentions to use genAI in their teaching are increasing (e.g., Markos et al., 2024). AI interventions to support PST learning was the second most frequent (44.9%, *n* = 62), followed by AI used for analysing ITE data (15.9%, e.g., clustering, Luik & Taimalu, 2023) and interventions to specifically assist with ITE teaching (2.9%, *n* = 4). The applications of AI were then classified into the four main thematic AI application areas (see Figure 1). As found by other reviews (e.g., Bond et al., 2024), more than half of the studies (55.8%, *n* = 77) explored applications or attitudes towards adaptive systems and personalisation (see Table 5). In contrast, only 13 studies investigated AI's use for assessment and evaluation, 12 studies employed profiling and prediction, and six studies focused on intelligent tutoring systems.

Table 5. Applications of AI in ITE.

Study focus ⁴	<i>n</i>	%
Adaptive systems and personalisation	77	55.8%

“AI” as one entity or idea	34	24.6%
Assessment and evaluation	13	9.4%
Profiling and prediction	12	8.7%
Intelligent tutoring systems	6	4.3%

Adaptive systems and personalisation

Studies about adaptive systems and personalisation were heavily focused on chatbots and genAI (33.3%, $n = 46$), followed by simulations/virtual reality (10.9%, $n = 15$), Natural language processing (NLP)-based automatic adaptive feedback or writing support system (4.3%, $n = 6$), facial and image recognition (4.3%, $n = 6$), and robots (4.3%, $n = 6$). Three studies (2.2%) explored the use of AI-based voice assistants or speech recognition, including a study by Halonen et al. (2023) that used automatic voice recognition to capture Finnish pre-service Science teachers’ co-creation of knowledge, which was then fed back to them through word clouds to stimulate reflections of their pedagogical content knowledge. Two further studies investigated recommender systems (Caglar-Ozhan et al., 2022; Hijón-Neira et al., 2023).

Chatbots and generative AI

The use of chatbots and genAI in ITE has been explored across a range of disciplines and countries, including South Africa where PSTs were able to use ChatGPT regardless of their physical location, but raised concerns about students’ general accessibility to AI infrastructure and connectivity (Tunjera & Chigona, 2023). Chatbots have been shown to improve PST critical thinking (e.g., Drushlyak et al., 2024), motivation (Fidan & Gencel, 2022), and creative thinking (Liu et al., 2023), although Ji et al. (2023) found that despite ChatGPT not positively impacting creativity or teaching competency, it did help PSTs with their understanding and application of STEM concepts and reduce their cognitive load. The use of chatbots within the Metaverse (Meta, 2024) has also been found to enhance student perceptions (Hwang et al., 2024) and increase their subject knowledge (Lee et al., 2024). Lesser researched applications include the use of Copilot (Microsoft, n.d.; see Siiman, 2024), AI-powered music applications such as Google’s Blob Opera (Google Arts & Culture, n.d.; see Uzumcu & Acilmis, 2024) and art generator Wonder (Wonder, 2024), although students who spent more time revising keywords showed less preference for using AI (Zhou, 2024). Another AI art generator, Midjourney (Midjourney, n.d.), was used by Art PSTs in Finland (Vartiainen & Tedre, 2023), who felt that it lacked embodiment and materiality but that it could assist students with ideation.

ChatGPT can be used to create lesson plans, which some studies found boosted PSTs creativity (Kartal, 2024) and saved them time (Mavropoulou & Koutsoukos, 2023). However, research reports that students did not always use ChatGPT to its full potential, sometimes creating inappropriate material (Lee & Zhai, 2024) and lessons that require substantial editing in order to cater for diverse contexts and learning needs (Durmus, 2024). Therefore, Kerneža (2023) reported on the cognitive processes and skills needed when using chatbots to create lesson plans, as identified by Slovenian PSTs, including abstract and critical thinking, creativity, cultural competence, problem solving, emotional intelligence, and an understanding of the language limitations of chatbots, and how they work. Going further than this, Mavropoulou & Koutsoukos (2023) used ChatGPT to create their entire secondary school Didactic Methodology course using structured prompts for developing the course outline, lesson plans,

assessment instructions and rubrics. They found that it provided satisfactory responses, although they did need to check and adjust the references that had been suggested, as ChatGPT is known to hallucinate this information. McLeod & Richardson (2023) also found that ChatGPT-generated rubrics and automated feedback improved their teaching efficiency, with PSTs offering neither positive nor negative critique, however the authors suggest that more time is needed to refine the prompt to provide richer feedback.

Simulations and virtual reality

The use of virtual worlds for teacher education has been around for more than two decades (see Warburton, 2009), helping PSTs teach whenever and wherever they want (Kelleci & Aksoy, 2021), preparing them for behavioural situations before they occur (e.g., Chen, 2022). Although perhaps not yet widely familiar with some PSTs and educators (Tural & Koçak, 2023), the Metaverse (Meta, 2024) is a series of virtual worlds where users can interact in a 3D space, much like they could in Second Life (e.g., Oh & Nussli, 2014). Whilst the Metaverse has shown positive results in regard to PST language teaching knowledge acquisition (Lee et al., 2024), research has also highlighted the need to use a chatbot (Hwang et al., 2024) or NPC tutor in order to help guide decision-making during virtual practicum activities (Agrati, 2023). Multi-source feedback and recommendations whilst using SimInClass (Simsoft, 2023) have also been shown to result in less negative emotions in PSTs (Caglar-Ozhan et al., 2022) as well as raised self-awareness and improved teaching skills (Kelleci Alkan et al., 2024). Research has found that PSTs value the use of simulations for their real-life problem-solving capabilities and humour (Dai et al., 2024), as well as enabling reflection on teaching practices (Slotte et al., 2023), although further development of simulation systems to make them more life-like has been suggested.

Automatic adaptive feedback and writing support

In a German study of 60 PSTs (Bauer et al., 2024), Epistemic Network Analysis was used to analyse learners' written explanations to simulated student cases, finding that adaptive feedback was more effective than static feedback, fostering diagnostic argumentation especially in collaborative learning contexts (Sailer et al., 2023). PSTs found that Scribo helped them focus on arguments and quotations, reducing their worry about writing errors, however their intertextuality was not improved (Martono et al., 2023). PSTs in Indonesia (Rizqa et al., 2022) also found that, although it could provide feedback at the sentence level, Scribo alone was not able to fully support academic level writing. Research on adaptive feedback also explored PST perceptions of AI, including a study by Kaufmann (2021) that found both in-service teachers and PSTs preferred advice from a human over an expert model. In contrast, when Ruwe & Mayweg-Paus (2023) told German PSTs that feedback was either from AI, from a peer or from an educator, results showed that PSTs ascribed more trustworthiness to AI. The authors suggest that practitioners use more personalised language in feedback, as formal language can be detrimental to motivation.

Facial and image recognition

The use of facial recognition has been used to understand teachers' movement patterns (e.g., Huang et al., 2023) and professional noticing (e.g., Kosko et al., 2021, October 14-17). Speech and facial recognition were also explored in a quasi-experimental study in Taiwan (Chang et

al., 2023), where a hands-on STEAM activity resulted in increased creativity and a more positive attitude for those PSTs in the experimental group, and another Taiwanese study involving speech and image recognition (Chou et al., 2023) led to improved technology acceptance and attitudes towards AI usability and usefulness. In an innovative use of image recognition and teaching machine learning concepts, PSTs in the USA designed lessons for middle school students including different AI tools, such as Quick, Draw! Machine Learning for Kids, and Guess Who (Farris, 2022).

Robots

Three studies explored PSTs attitudes towards robots, finding that both Slovenian and Russian PSTs were opposed to using human-like social robots in teaching, with the perceived social dimension of the social robot identified as the most important construct (Istenič et al., 2021; Istenič et al., 2024; Rosanda & Istenič, 2021). A further study in Slovenia stressed the need for future research to explore the sociological, psychological and ethical dimensions behind PSTs engagement with robots (Zemljak & Kerneža, 2024), and a Teacher Robot competition in South Africa was held during a semester course, where students needed to articulate their vision of how AI and robots could improve the lives of students (Petersen & Batchelor, 2019). The findings revealed that PSTs saw robots as static, programmable tools, there to improve teacher efficiency and address learner needs, indicating limited creativity towards their potential uses.

Assessment and evaluation

12 studies (8.7%) focused specifically on how AI could be used for automating assessment and evaluation, outside of the use of tools such as NLP to give formative feedback or writing support (see Adaptive Systems & Personalisation); eight studies (5.8%) explored the use of automated grading or writing systems, and four studies (2.9%) used NLP to help analyse and evaluate teaching practices. For example, four PSTs assessed the writing of 2,176 high school and university Science students in the Philippines against a five-tiered scoring rubric, and then compared their assessment against an automated scoring system, which showed a strong level of consistency (Yoo et al., 2024). However, in a study exploring 89 PSTs blind comparison of ChatGPT-generated versus expert-generated scoring and feedback of texts written by Year 10 students, only 23% preferred the ChatGPT-generated feedback (Jansen et al., 2024).

Machine learning models have also been used to assess written reflections to determine reflective depth (e.g., Zhang et al., 2023), computational thinking and attitudes (e.g., Cutumisu & Guo, 2019), PSTs attention to classroom events (Wulff et al., 2022), and teaching quality (e.g., Xu et al., 2024). Wulff et al. (2023a) found that a pretrained language model using BERT outperformed other deep learning algorithms when analysing 92 PST physics teachers written reflections, which the authors also used to analyse the written reflections of 110 pre- and in-service physics teachers to identify aspects of quality, with experts agreeing with 72.2% of the ML estimations (Mientus et al., 2023). The authors also compared the reflections of physics PSTs ($n = 81$) compared to non-physics PSTs ($n = 68$) to see whether the model that was trained on physics education research content could accurately classify other disciplines (Wulff et al., 2023b). They found that it had acceptable performance for higher-level reasoning but needed to be finetuned with data from non-physics teachers for better performance. However, in another German study (Zhang et al., 2024), BigBird and Longformer models significantly

outperformed BERT, with the authors stressing the need to train models on various pedagogical strategies and educational theories, such as constructivism, which may then better align with current teaching approaches.

Profiling and prediction

12 studies (8.6%) explored AI for profiling and prediction, with multiple studies using machine learning algorithms to profile students (3.6%, $n = 5$) or to predict their academic achievement (2.9%, $n = 4$). The remaining studies investigated AI applications for identifying PSTs at risk of dropping out and improving retention (0.7%, $n = 1$); predicting subject-related content (0.7%, $n = 1$); and profiling instructors to forecast teaching performance (0.7%, $n = 1$). For example, Belland et al. (2022) used sentiment analysis to predict the quality of lesson plans by pre-service early childhood education teachers. They found that it could significantly predict lesson plan quality, pointing towards AI's potential in providing feedback and support during practicum experiences. Similarly, Akgün & Demir (2018) used artificial neural networks (ANNs) to predict elementary PSTs' academic achievement in a Science and Technology Education course. Using transcript data from 865 recent graduates of four Turkish universities, the ANN model achieved an R-value of 0.84, indicating its effectiveness in predicting academic achievement in social science courses.

Jin & Cutumisu (2023) investigated machine learning algorithms to predict the computational thinking (CT) skills of 93 PSTs. They trained decision tree, logistic regression, naïve Bayes, and k-nearest neighbor models on data from an online CT training platform, with the decision tree model showing the highest accuracy in predicting low-performing PSTs. AI has also been used to identify PSTs who may excel in diverse classroom settings; Arpaci et al. (2024) employed a multimodal analysis integrating structural equation modelling (SEM), deep learning, and ANNs to examine factors impacting teachers' sense of efficacy. Data from 1,061 PSTs showed a strong positive association between culturally responsive classroom management self-efficacy (CRCMSE) and overall teacher efficacy. Similarly, Luik & Taimalu (2023) and Schmid et al. (2021) used unsupervised machine learning techniques to profile PSTs based on their self-reported technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). While these models did not directly forecast teaching performance or predict PSTs' actual technology use, the findings suggested that using AI to profile PSTs using their TPACK scores can offer valuable insights into their teaching competencies, potentially informing the design of more effective training programmes.

Shifting focus to PST dropout, Singh & Alhulail (2022) investigated the use of a machine learning algorithm to predict PST dropout. Analysing data from 1,723 PSTs in Ethiopia, the study revealed that the model successfully predicted dropout, highlighting academic performance and aspirations as the strongest predictors of PST attrition. Finally, the studies highlight AI's potential in predicting subject-specific content and informing teaching practices. Abouelenein & Nagy Elmaadaway (2023) focused on a neuro-computerised virtual learning environment for pre-service maths teachers and demonstrated an ANN's ability to predict soil penetration resistance, showcasing AI's capability to model complex phenomena and provide insights that inform practical decisions. Wang et al. (2024) found that explainable AI can

enhance PSTs' trust in AI-generated analyses of classroom dialogue, providing support for the adoption of AI tools for informed decision-making in teaching practices.

Intelligent tutoring systems

Six studies (4.3%) specifically examined the use of Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITSs). Most of these studies focused on using ITSs to teach course content (3.6%, $n = 5$) or to diagnose student strengths and gaps in knowledge and provide automated feedback (2.9%, $n = 4$). Fewer studies investigated the use of ITSs for curating learning materials (1.5%, $n = 2$) and for assessing student acceptance of ITSs (1.5%, $n = 2$). For example, Stott & Hattingh (2015) used an ITS to teach the concept of density among 50 final year pre-service student teachers in a South African university, concluding that ITSs can be valuable tools for supplementing traditional teaching methods, especially in contexts where personalised instruction might be challenging due to time constraints or varied student needs. Similarly, Ballantyne et al. (2021) explored the use of an ITS designed to enhance English language proficiency among six PSTs. The study found that the participants had positive attitudes towards the system, valuing its personalised learning pathways and feedback mechanisms. However, they also expressed a preference for human tutors, highlighting the importance of the social and communicative aspects of learning that ITSs may lack. This aligns with Smith's (2018) findings, where 17 PSTs expressed positive views of adaptive systems, believing them to be beneficial for student learning—especially due to features like immediate feedback and self-paced learning—but that they should be used to supplement, not replace, traditional instruction.

The studies also offer insights into the value of ITSs for supporting PSTs in developing their technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). Huang et al. (2021), for example, found that PSTs who engaged in more metacognitive monitoring while using a computer-based learning environment (CBLE) called nBrowser demonstrated a more sophisticated understanding of TPACK and designed higher-quality technology-integrated lesson plans. However, Poitras et al.'s (2019) findings offer a more nuanced perspective, showing that while the dynamic version of nBrowser positively influenced pre-service teachers' information-seeking behaviours, it did not lead to significantly different learning outcomes compared to the static version. This suggests that enhancing learning efficiency might not always translate into improved learning efficacy in terms of knowledge acquisition or task performance.

Discussion

This systematic mapping review explored research on the use of AI within initial teacher education through an analysis of 138 studies, published in the last decade. The results show that there has been a huge rise in the number of studies undertaken since the COVID-19 pandemic, but especially since the advancements of genAI increased the attention being given to the role of AI in education (Bozkurt & Sharma, 2023; Lo, 2023). This was reflected in the authorship of studies in this review, with 58.7% of first authors coming from an Education faculty, far more than was found by earlier AI research (e.g., Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019), as well as a widespread global interest. Research has been conducted in 41 different countries, including Nigeria, Slovenia, Indonesia and Ethiopia, with a higher percentage of Middle Eastern and African authorship than has been found in other AI reviews (e.g., Bond et al., 2024). However, there were only two studies undertaken in Oceania (both in Australia) and there was

no research found from South America, although this might indicate that South American authors are publishing in their native languages to have more impact within their own contexts. Unfortunately, it was not possible to gain a complete understanding of where research has been undertaken, as 8% of studies did not state where the research was conducted, and a quarter of studies did not disclose which subject area or educational level their PSTs were specialising in. Missing study design information is an ongoing issue in EdTech research (e.g., Forsström et al., 2024), which inhibits the applicability to practice and future research.

AI research was mostly undertaken with PSTs in Science, English and Maths specialities, with applications for primary schools more investigated than those for secondary schools. This is interesting, given that a recent review of AI in K-12 classrooms (Crompton et al., 2024) found a more balanced distribution between primary (35%), middle (29%) and secondary schools (36%). The majority of studies in this review (57.2%) used quantitative approaches, especially surveys, with only a small number of studies using a range of data. Only 13.8% of studies captured data across a one semester period, with many studies being experiments lasting one day or less, or surveys taken at one time point, likely due to trying to capture initial reactions to recent AI developments. Only half of all studies included explicit information about participant consent, and many studies explicitly stated that they could not share their data due to confidentiality or European data sharing laws, despite recent calls for increased attention to ethics in AI research (e.g., Bond et al., 2024).

ITE research has been heavily dominated by studies that explore PST AI awareness, trust, acceptance, self-efficacy, AI literacy, intention to use AI in their own learning, and their intention to teach using AI, with a very small number of studies explicitly investigating support for ITE educators (see Figure 5). Adaptive systems and personalisation were the most researched (55.8%), with a strong interest in chatbots and genAI representing a third of studies, followed by assessment and evaluation (9.4%), profiling and prediction (8.7%) and intelligent tutoring systems (4.3%). Chatbots and genAI have the capacity to improve critical and creative thinking, motivation, cognitive load, problem solving and subject knowledge (e.g., Ji et al., 2023), and they can be used for initial ideation and brainstorming (e.g., Vartiainen & Tedre, 2023), creating lesson plans and course outlines (e.g., Mavropoulou & Koutsoukos, 2023), creating assessment tasks, rubrics, and giving automated feedback (e.g., McLeod & Richardson, 2023). However, research stresses the need for PSTs to first understand how they work, and what AI systems are and are not capable of (Kerneža, 2023), as well as a lot of work needed in refining prompts and teaching prompt engineering (e.g., Moorhouse et al., 2024; Tirado-Olivares et al., 2023).

Figure 5. Applications of AI in ITE research (2015 – 2024).

Virtual classroom simulations, such as SimInClass, EVETeach and the Metaverse, can help prepare PSTs for a number of difficult situations before they step into a school (e.g., Schussler et al., 2017), helping them to develop content knowledge, raise self-awareness and improve their teaching skills. AI can be used to capture and analyse PST behaviours in the classroom, or to facilitate further discussion and reflection within collaborative activities (e.g., Chang et al., 2023). A small amount of research has also explored how machine learning concepts can be taught using AI-enabled tools (e.g., Farris, 2022), although further exploration of how PSTs can build confidence and teaching skills through the use of AI is needed (e.g., Hur, 2024). The evidence has been mixed about PSTs willingness to trust AI feedback, although adaptive feedback whilst writing or whilst in a simulated environment can provide opportunities for deeper reflection and critical thinking (e.g., Sailer et al., 2023). Less research has been undertaken on PSTs and automated grading, with more of a focus on the use of AI to evaluate lesson plan quality, attention to classroom events and reflection. AI can also be used to help understand how PSTs are travelling, especially in the first semester (Singh & Alhulail, 2022), including understanding what their interests are or to get feedback about a topic (Cutumisu & Guo, 2019). Given the teacher recruitment crisis being experienced by many countries around the world (UNESCO, 2022), the use of AI to help predict PSTs who are at risk of dropping out could be particularly helpful. However, only five studies explored the prediction of academic achievement or drop out.

Implications for policy and practice

There is an overwhelming need to raise PST digital and AI literacy across all ITE subjects (UNESCO, 2024b), building confidence through practical, hands-on, real-world tasks, including a focus on ethics and data privacy, supported by continuous feedback (Bae et al.,

2024). However, PSTs need to be taught problem solving and critical thinking skills first (e.g., Lim, 2023) with an increased focus on digital skills generally. Teacher educators should prioritise the development of foundational skills that will allow PSTs to evaluate and adapt to different AI tools and approaches. To that end, policies and strategies need to be established at the top level first, with policymakers working collaboratively with developers, institutions and educators to ensure that provision is ethical, accessible and inclusive (Ma & Lei, 2024; Markos et al., 2024), in order to lead to positive outcomes for both PSTs and students. Further support for ongoing in-service teacher professional development is also needed (UNESCO, 2024b), fostering ongoing collaboration with AI industry leaders (e.g., Adelana et al., 2024), with one suggestion being internship or practicum opportunities to help the development of authentic learning resources, whilst also feeding pedagogical ideas back into the development pipeline (Mohammed et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2024).

Implications for future research

The findings reveal a need for research to be undertaken in a wider range of contexts, such as ITE subjects outside of Science, Maths and English (e.g., skills-based subjects, Liu et al., 2023), research in different countries, cultures and educational systems (e.g., Zhang & Zhang, 2024) such as in South America, as well as with larger diverse student and ITE educator populations (e.g., Bae et al., 2024). Mixed methods studies that synthesise a range of data are particularly welcome, including the use of design-based, practitioner-led approaches. Research that explores causal relationships and the impact of AI on PST, teacher educator and student outcomes could provide deeper insights (e.g., Jansen et al., 2024), particularly when explored across a semester or longer. Suggestions for AI development include systems that capture posture, movement and emotions (Ezquerria et al., 2023), ITSs that integrate LLMs to facilitate conversational problem-solving (Gattupalli et al., 2023), more sophisticated NLP and algorithms that are trained on contextually relevant data (Song et al., 2022), and further exploration of explainable models to help enrich feedback (Xu et al., 2024). Finally, particularly imperative is the need for future empirical research to include complete study design information (Bond et al., 2024), including where the research was undertaken, who the participants were, when the data was captured, how long the study lasted, what ethical procedures were followed, and a data availability statement (see Koren et al., 2022).

Conclusion

The increasing interest in the use of AI for teaching and learning, along with the growing recognition that AI literacy and skills are becoming essential for the future, highlights the importance of understanding how ITE has been used in HE to prepare PSTs for this fast-evolving landscape. However, within the domain of ITE, there remains a paucity of research focusing on how AI is being integrated into training curricula and practices, as well as its impacts. This systematic mapping review has begun to unveil the emerging yet intricate landscape of AI research in ITE, revealing new and significant developments. Notably, the review has highlighted a growing interest in adaptive systems, particularly genAI, along with a dominance of quantitative approaches and a prevalence of studies exploring PSTs' awareness and acceptance of AI, with limited focus on the impact of AI on learning outcomes or on supporting teacher educators. It has also revealed a need to build PSTs' AI confidence and problem-solving skills through real-world tasks, with a particular focus on ethics and data

privacy. Future policy should include clear ethical guidelines for the use of AI in HE, not only with regard to the privacy and data protection of students, but also in the ethical use of AI in real world settings, including schools. Addressing these gaps will be crucial for ensuring the ethical and effective integration of AI in ITE, ultimately enhancing the preparedness of future educators for the evolving digital landscape in education.

Pre-print

Notes

¹ <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/eppi-vis/login/open?webdbid=701>

² See Bond, Oxley, et al. (2024) for further exploration of authorship characteristics.

³ See Bond, Oxley, et al. (2024) and the [web database](#) for the full list.

⁴ Some studies had more than one focus.

Pre-print

References

* indicates inclusion in the corpus of 138 included studies

- * Abouelenein, Y. A. M., & Nagy Elmaadaway, M. A. (2023). Impact of teaching a neuro-computerized course through VLE to develop computational thinking among mathematics pre-service teachers. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 61(6), 1175–1206. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07356331231165099>
- * Adelana, O. P., Ayanwale, M. A., & Sanusi, I. T. (2024). Exploring pre-service biology teachers' intention to teach genetics using an AI intelligent tutoring-based system. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2310976. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2310976>
- * Akgün, E., & Demir, M. (2018). Modeling course achievements of elementary education teacher candidates with artificial neural networks. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 5(3), 491–509. <https://doi.org/10.21449/ijate.444073>
- Agrati, L. S. (2023). Tutoring in the metaverse. Study on student-teachers' and tutors' perceptions about NPC tutor. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, Article 1202442. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1202442>
- Alqahtani, T., Badreldin, H. A., Alrashed, M., Alshaya, A. I., Alghamdi, S. S., bin Saleh, K., Alowais, S. A., Alshaya, O. A., Rahman, I., Al Yami, M.S., & Albekairy, A. M. (2023). The emergent role of artificial intelligence, natural learning processing, and large language models in higher education and research. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, 19(8), 1236-1242.
- Ansari, A. N., Ahmad, S., & Bhutta, S. M. (2024). Mapping the global evidence around the use of ChatGPT in higher education: A systematic scoping review. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(9), 11281–11321. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12223-4>
- * Arpacı, I., Karataş, K., Gün, F., & Süer, S. (2024). Predicting teachers' sense of efficacy: A multimodal analysis integrating SEM, deep learning, and ANN. *Psychology in the Schools*, 61(8), 3373–3389. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.23222>
- * Bae, H., Hur, J., Park, J., Choi, G. W., & Moon, J. (2024). Pre-service teachers' dual perspectives on generative AI: Benefits, challenges, and integrating into teaching and learning. *Online Learning Journal*, 28(3). <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v28i3.4543>
- Baker, T., & Smith, L. (2019). *Educ-AI-tion rebooted? Exploring the future of artificial intelligence in schools and colleges*. https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/Future_of_AI_and_education_v5_WEB.Pdf
- * Ballantyne, D., Livingston, C., & Garraway, J. (2021). Cultural-historical activity theory as a framework for exploring pre-service teachers' use of an intelligent tutoring system for English language proficiency. *Africa Education Review*, 18(3-4), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18146627.2022.2150245>
- * Bauer, E., Sailer, M., Kiesewetter, J., Fischer, M. R., Gurevych, I., & Fischer, F. (2023). Facilitating justification, disconfirmation, and transparency in diagnostic argumentation: Effects of automatic adaptive feedback in teacher education. *Zeitschrift für Pädagogische Psychologie*, 38(1-2). <https://doi.org/10.1024/1010-0652/a000363>
- * Belland, B. R., Kim, C., Zhang, A. Y., Lee, E., & Dinç, E. (2022). Classifying the quality of robotics-enhanced lesson plans using motivation variables, word count, and sentiment analysis of reflections. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 69, 102058. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2022.102058>
- Bond, M., Khosravi, H., De Laat, M., Bergdahl, N., Negrea, V., Oxley, E., Pham, P., Chong, S.W., & Siemens, G. (2024). A meta systematic review of artificial intelligence in higher education: A call for increased ethics, collaboration, and rigour. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 21(4). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00436-z>
- Bond, M., Oxley, E., & Lymperis, L. (2024) *AI & ITE: A systematic mapping review*. OSF. https://osf.io/5a3ub/?view_only=b3537a7aabf64d86afebd8402a54bbd7
- Bozkurt, A., & Sharma, R. C. (2023). Challenging the status quo and exploring the new boundaries in the age of algorithms: Reimagining the role of generative AI in distance education and online learning. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 18(1), i-viii. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7755273>

- Bozkurt, A., Xiao, J., Lambert, S., Pazurek, A., Crompton, H., Koseoglu, S., Farrow, R., Bond, M., Nerantzi, C., Honeychurch, S., Bali, M., Dron, J., Mir, K., Stewart, B., Costello, E., Mason, J., Stracke, C. M., Romero-Hall, E., Koutropoulos, A., ... Jandrić, P. (2023). Speculative futures on ChatGPT and generative Artificial Intelligence (AI): A collective reflection from the educational landscape. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 18(1), 1–78. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7636568>
- * Caglar-Ozhan, S., Altun, A., & Ekmekcioglu, E. (2022). Emotional patterns in a simulated virtual classroom supported with an affective recommendation system. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 53(6), 1724–1749. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13209>
- Celik, I., Dindar, M., Muukkonen, H., & Järvelä, S. (2022). The promises and challenges of artificial intelligence for teachers: A systematic review of research. *TechTrends*, 66(4), 616–630.
- * Chang, Y.-S., Wang, Y.-Y., & Ku, Y.-T. (2023). Influence of online STEAM hands-on learning on AI learning, creativity, and creative emotions. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2023.2205898>
- * Chen, C.-Y. (2022). Immersive virtual reality to train preservice teachers in managing students' challenging behaviours: A pilot study. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 53(4), 998–1024. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13181>
- * Chou, C.-M., Shen, T.-C, Shen, T.-C, Shen, C.-H., & Liu, T.-L. (2023, June 16-18). *Promoting pre-service teachers' AI-supported application of self-efficacy* [Paper presentation]. 2023 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Software Engineering and Artificial Intelligence (SEAI), Xiamen, China. IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SEAI59139.2023.10217712>
- Cope, B., Kalantzis, M., & Sears-Smith, D. (2020). Artificial intelligence for education: Knowledge and its assessment in AI-enabled learning ecologies. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 53(12), 1229–1245. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2020.1728732>
- Cordeschi, R. (2007). AI turns fifty: Revisiting its origins. *Applied Artificial Intelligence*, 21(4-5), 259–279.
- Crompton, H., Jones, M. V., & Burke, D. (2024). Affordances and challenges of artificial intelligence in K-12 education: A systematic review. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 56(3), 248–268. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2022.2121344>
- * Cutumisu, M., & Guo, Q. (2019). Using topic modeling to extract pre-service teachers' understandings of computational thinking from their coding reflections. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 62(4), 325–332. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2019.2925253>
- * Dai, C.-P., Ke, F., Zhang, N., Barrett, A., West, L., Bhowmik, S., Southerland, S. A., & Yuan, X. (2024, May 11-16). *Designing conversational agents to support student teacher learning in virtual reality simulation: A case study* [Conference paper]. CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, Honolulu, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613905.3637145>
- DfE [Department for Education] (2023). *Generative AI in education. Call for evidence: Summary of responses*. Department for Education. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/65609be50c7ec8000d95bddd/Generative_AI_all_for_evidence_summary_of_responses.pdf
- DfE [Department for Education] (2024). *Generative AI in education: Educator and expert views*. Department for Education. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/65b8cd41b5cb6e000d8bb74e/DfE_GenAI_in_education_-_Educator_and_expert_views_report.pdf
- Digital Solution Foundry, & EPPI-Centre. (2023). *EPPI-Mapper* (Version 2.2.3) [Computer software]. UCL Social Research
- * Drushlyak, M., Lukashova, T., Sabadosh, Y., Melnikov, I., & Semenikhina, O. (2024, May 20-24). *Using ChatGPT for the development of critical thinking in youth: Example of inequality proof*. [Conference paper]. 47th MIPRO ICT and Electronics Convention (MIPRO), Opatija, Croatia. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIPRO60963.2024.10569759>
- * Durmus, C. (2024, June 18–21). *From AI-generated lesson plans to the real-life classes: Explored by pre-service teachers* [Conference paper]. 10th International Conference on Higher Education

- Advances (HEAd'24)*, Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain. <https://doi.org/10.4995/HEAd24.2024.17060>
- EPPI-Centre (n.d.). *EPPI-Reviewer*. UCL Social Research Institute. <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/cms/Default.aspx?tabid=3790>
- European Commission (2020). *Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027: Resetting education and training for the digital age*. European Commission. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0624>
- * Ezquerra, A., Agen, F., Toma, R. B., & Ezquerra-Romano, I. (2023). Using facial emotion recognition to research emotional phases in an inquiry-based science activity. *Research in Science & Technological Education*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02635143.2023.2232995>
- Farjon, D., Smits, A., & Voogt, J. (2019). Technology integration of pre-service teachers explained by attitudes and beliefs, competency, access, and experience. *Computers & Education*, 130, 81-93.
- * Farris, A. V. (2022, November 11-12). *Preservice teachers' mechanistic reasoning about machine learning and artificial intelligence*. [Conference paper]. 2022 ASEE Middle Atlantic Section Conference, Penn State Harrisburg, PA, USA. <https://par.nsf.gov/servlets/purl/10379636>
- * Fidan, M., & Gencel, N. (2022). Supporting the instructional videos with chatbot and peer feedback mechanisms in online learning: The effects on learning performance and intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 60(7), 1716–1741. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07356331221077901>
- Forsström, S., Bond, M., & Njå, M. (2024). *A meta-scoping review of programming and robotics in primary and secondary education*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13828461>
- García-Gorrostieta, J. M., López-López, A., & González-López, S. (2018). Automatic argument assessment of final project reports of computer engineering students. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, 26(5), 1217-1226. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cae.21996>
- * Gattupalli S, Lee W, Alessio D, Crabtree D, Arroyo I, & Woolf B (2023, July 7). *Exploring pre-service teachers' perceptions of Large Language Models-generated hints in online mathematics learning* [Conference paper]. AIED2023 Empowering Education with LLMs - the Next-Gen Interface and Content Generation, Tokyo, Japan. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3487/paper10.pdf>
- Gedrimiene, E., Celik, I., Kaasila, A., Mäkitalo, K., & Muukkonen, H. (2024). Artificial intelligence (AI)-enhanced learning analytics (LA) for supporting career decisions: Advantages and challenges from user perspective. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(1), 297-322. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12277-4>
- * Getenet, S. (2024). Pre-service teachers and ChatGPT in multistrategy problem-solving: Implications for mathematics teaching in primary schools. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 19(1), em0766. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/14141>
- González-Calatayud, V., Prendes-Espinosa, P., & Roig-Vila, R. (2021). Artificial intelligence for student assessment: A systematic review. *Applied Sciences*, 11(12), 5467. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11125467>
- Google Arts & Culture (n.d.). *Blob opera*. <https://artsandculture.google.com/project/blob-opera>
- Gough, D., Oliver, S., & Thomas, J. (Eds.). (2012). *An introduction to systematic reviews*. SAGE.
- Gusenbauer, M., & Haddaway, N. R. (2020). Which academic search systems are suitable for systematic reviews or meta-Analyses? Evaluating retrieval qualities of Google Scholar, PubMed and 26 other resources. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 11(2), 181–217. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1378>
- * Halonen, N., Ståhle, P., Juuti, K., Paavola, S., & Lonka, K. (2023). Catalyst for co-construction: The role of AI-directed speech recognition technology in the self-organization of knowledge. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, 1232423. Frontiers Media SA.
- Han, B., Nawaz, S., Buchanan, G., & McKay, D. (2023, July 3-7). *Ethical and pedagogical impacts of AI in education* [Conference paper]. International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Education, Tokyo, Japan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-36272-9_54
- * Han, J., Rhee, W., & Cho, Y. H. (2018, October 26-28). *Real-time detection of low-achieving groups in face-to-face computer-supported collaborative learning* [Conference paper]. 10th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers (ICETC), Tokyo, Japan. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290511.3290565>

-
- Harzing, A.W. (2007). *Publish or Perish*. <https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish>
- * Hijón-Neira, R., Connolly, C., Pizarro, C., & Pérez-Marín, D. (2023). Prototype of a recommendation model with artificial intelligence for computational thinking improvement of secondary education students. *Computers*, 12(6), 113. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers12060113>
- Holmes, W., Porayska-Pomsta, K., Holstein, K., Sutherland, E., Baker, T., Shum, S. B., Santos, O. C., Rodrigo, M. T., Cukurova, M., Bittencourt, I. I., & Koedinger, K. R. (2022). Ethics of AI in education: Towards a community-wide framework. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 1-23. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40593-021-00239-1>
- * Huang, L., Li, S., Poitras, E., & Lajoie, S. P. (2021). Latent profiles of self-regulated learning and their impacts on teachers' technology integration. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 52(2), 695–713. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13050>
- * Huang, Y., Richter, E., Kleickmann, T., Scheiter, K., & Richter, D. (2023). Body in motion, attention in focus: A virtual reality study on teachers' movement patterns and noticing. *Part of Special Issue: Learning with ICT: New Perspectives on Help Seeking and Information Searching*, 206, 104912. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104912>
- * Hur, J. W. (2024). Fostering AI literacy: overcoming concerns and nurturing confidence among preservice teachers. *Information and Learning Sciences*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ILS-11-2023-0170>
- * Hwang, Y., Lee, S., & Jeon, J. (2024). Integrating AI chatbots into the metaverse: Pre-service English teachers' design works and perceptions. *Education and Information Technologies*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-12924-4>
- * Istenič, A., Bratko, I., & Rosanda, V. (2021). Are pre-service teachers disinclined to utilise embodied humanoid social robots in the classroom? *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 52(6), 2340–2358. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13144>
- * Istenič, A., Latypova, L., Rosanda, V., Turk, Ž., Valeeva, R., & Zhai, X. (2024). Reluctance to authenticity-imbued social robots as child-interaction partners. *Education Sciences*, 14(4), 390. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14040390>
- * Jansen, T., Höft, L., Bahr, L., Fleckenstein, J., Möller, J., Köller, O., & Meyer, J. (2024). Empirische arbeit: Comparing generative ai and expert feedback to students' writing: Insights from student teachers. *Psychologie in Erziehung Und Unterricht*, 71(2), 80–92. <https://doi.org/10.2378/peu2024.art08d>
- * Ji, Y., Zou, X., Li, T., & Zhan, Z. (2023, November 3-5). *The effectiveness of ChatGPT on pre-service teachers' STEM teaching literacy, learning performance, and cognitive load in a teacher training course* [Conference paper]. 6th International Conference on Educational Technology Management (ICETM 2023), Guangzhu, China. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3637907.3637948>
- * Jin, H.-Y., & Cutumisu, M. (2023). Predicting pre-service teachers' computational thinking skills using machine learning classifiers. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11642-7>
- * Kartal, G. (2024). The influence of ChatGPT on thinking skills and creativity of EFL student teachers: A narrative inquiry. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 50(4), 627–642. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2024.2326502>
- * Kaufmann, E. (2021). Algorithm appreciation or aversion? Comparing in-service and pre-service teachers' acceptance of computerized expert models. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 2, 100028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100028>
- * Kelleci, Ö., & Aksoy, N. C. (2021). Using game-based virtual classroom simulation in teacher training: User experience research. *Simulation & Gaming*, 52(2), 204–225. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878120962152>
- * Kelleci Alkan, Ö., Aksoy, N. C., Kulaksız, T., Kaplan, H. A., Durmaz, B. N., Özcan, M., & Kalkavan, B. (2024). A multi-feedback system integrated simulation-based teacher training to scaffold pre-service teachers' teaching skills: A phenomenological approach. *Education and Information Technologies*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-12657-4>
- * Kerneža, M. (2023). Fundamental and basic cognitive skills required for teachers to effectively use chatbots in education. In *Science and Technology Education: New Developments and Innovations* (pp. 99–110). Scientia Socialis Press. <https://doi.org/10.33225/BalticSTE/2023.99>

-
- Khosravi, H., Shum, S. B., Chen, G., Conati, C., Tsai, Y. S., Kay, J., Knight, S., Martinez-Maldonado, R., Sadiq, S., & Gašević, D. (2022). Explainable artificial intelligence in education. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 3, 100074.
- Koren, M., Connolly, M., Lull, J., & Vilhuber, L. (2022). *Data and Code Availability Standard Website*. <https://datacodestandard.org> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7436134>
- * Kosko, K. W., Yang, Y., Austin, C., Guan, Q., Gandolfi, E., & Gu, Z. (2021, October 14-17). *Examining preservice teachers' professional noticing of students' mathematics through 360 video and machine learning* [Paper presentation]. 43rd annual meeting of the North American Chapter for the Psychology of Mathematics Education, Philadelphia. Psychology of Mathematics Education-North America. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED630169.pdf>
- Lampropoulos, G. (2023). Augmented reality and artificial intelligence in education: Toward immersive intelligent tutoring systems. In: V. Geroimenko (Ed.), *Augmented Reality and Artificial Intelligence. Springer Series on Cultural Computing* (pp. 137–146). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-27166-3_8
- Landis, J. R., & Koch, G. G. (1977). The measurement of observer agreement for categorical data. *Biometrics*, 33(1), 159. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2529310>
- Langran, E., Searson, M., & Trumble, J. (2024). Transforming teacher education in the age of generative AI. In M. Searson, E. Langran, & J. Tru (Eds.), *Exploring new horizons: Generative artificial intelligence and teacher education* (pp. 2-13). Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE).
- * Lee, G.-G., & Zhai, X. (2024). Using ChatGPT for science learning: A study on pre-service teachers' lesson planning. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 17, 1683–1700. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2024.3401457>
- * Lee, S., Jeon, J., & Choe, H. (2024). Enhancing pre-service teachers' Global Englishes awareness with technology: A focus on AI chatbots in 3D metaverse environments. *TESOL Quarterly*, Article tesq.3300. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.3300>
- * Lim, E. M. (2023). The effects of pre-service early childhood teachers' digital literacy and self-efficacy on their perception of AI education for young children. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(10), 12969-12995. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11724-6>
- Lin, C. C., Huang, A. Y., & Lu, O. H. (2023). Artificial intelligence in intelligent tutoring systems toward sustainable education: A systematic review. *Smart Learning Environments*, 10(1), 41. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-023-00260-y>
- * Liu, Z., Vobolevich, A., & Oparin, A. (2023). The influence of AI ChatGPT on improving teachers' creative thinking. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 22(12), 124–139. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.22.12.7>
- Lo, C. K. (2023). What is the impact of ChatGPT on education? A rapid review of the literature. *Education Sciences*, 13(4), 410. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13040410>
- Luckin, R., Holmes, W., Griffiths, M., & Forcier, L. B. (2016). *Intelligence unleashed: An argument for AI in education*. Pearson Education.
- * Luik, P., & Taimalu, M. (2023, March 18-20). *Professional knowledge clusters of student teachers based on the TPACK framework* [Conference paper]. 11th International Conference on Information and Education Technology (ICIET 2023), Fujisawa, Japan. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIET56899.2023.10111442>
- * Ma, S., & Lei, L. (2024). The factors influencing teacher education students' willingness to adopt artificial intelligence technology for information-based teaching. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 44(1), 94-111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2024.2305155>
- * Markos, A., Prentzas, J., & Sidiropoulou, M. (2024). Pre-service teachers' assessment of ChatGPT's utility in higher education: SWOT and content analysis. *Electronics*, 13(10), 1985. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics13101985>
- * Martono, N., Drajadi, N. A., Rochsantiningsih, D., & Wijaya, S. A. (2023). Intertextuality in pre-service teachers' argumentative essay in raising AI: Practices and beliefs. *Register Journal*, 16(2), 186–206. <https://doi.org/10.18326/register.v16i2.186-206>

- * Mavropoulou E, & Koutsoukos, M. (2023). Integration of Artificial Intelligence on teaching the course of didactic methodology: A case study. *European Journal of Social Science Education and Research*, 10(3), 36-51. <https://revistia.com/index.php/ejsr/article/view/6992>
- * McLeod, A., & Richardson, H. (2023). Co-constructing skills for ChatGPT at university. *Journal of Academic Language and Learning*, 17(1), T70-T80. <https://journal.aall.org.au/index.php/jall/article/view/929>
- Menabò, L., Sansavini, A., Brighi, A., Skrzypiec, G., & Guarini, A. (2021). Promoting the integration of technology in teaching: An analysis of the factors that increase the intention to use technologies among Italian teachers. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 37(6), 1566-1577.
- Meta (2024). *What is the Metaverse?* <https://about.meta.com/what-is-the-metaverse/>
- Microsoft (n.d.). *Microsoft Copilot*. <https://copilot.microsoft.com>
- Midjourney (n.d.). *MidJourney*. <https://www.midjourney.com>
- * Mientus, L., Wulff, P., Nowak, A., & Borowski, A. (2023). Fast-and-frugal means to assess reflection-related reasoning processes in teacher training—Development and evaluation of a scalable machine learning-based metric. *Zeitschrift Für Erziehungswissenschaft*, 26(3), 677–702. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11618-023-01166-8>
- * Mnguni, L. (2024). A qualitative analysis of South African pre-service life sciences teachers' behavioral intentions for integrating AI in teaching. *Journal for STEM Education Research*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41979-024-00128-x>
- * Mohammed, A., Ali, R., & Alharbi, AAB. (2021). The reality of using Artificial Intelligence techniques in teacher preparation programs in light of the opinions of faculty members: A case study in Saudi Qassim University. *Multicultural Education*, 7(1), 5-16. <http://ijdri.com/me/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/2.pdf>
- Montenegro-Rueda, M., Fernández-Cerero, J., Fernández-Batanero, J. M., & López-Meneses, E. (2023). Impact of the implementation of ChatGPT in education: A systematic review. *Computers*, 12(8), 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers12080153>
- * Moorhouse, B. L., Wan, Y., Wu, C., Kohnke, L., Ho, T. Y., & Kwong, T. (2024). Developing language teachers' professional generative AI competence: An intervention study in an initial language teacher education course. *System*, 125, 103399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2024.103399>
- Mousavinasab, E., Zarifsaiaey, N., R. Niakan Kalhori, S., Rakhshan, M., Keikha, L., & Ghazi Saeedi, M. (2018). Intelligent tutoring systems: A systematic review of characteristics, applications, and evaluation methods. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 29(1), 142–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2018.1558257>
- Oh, K., & Nussli, N. (2014). Teacher training in the use of a three-dimensional immersive virtual world: Building understanding through first-hand experiences. *Journal of Teaching and Learning with Technology*, 3(1), 33–58. <https://doi.org/10.14434/jotlt.v3n1.3956>
- Ouyang, F., & Zhang, L. (2024). AI-driven learning analytics applications and tools in computer-supported collaborative learning: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 44, 100616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2024.100616>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., & Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, 372, n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
- * Petersen N, & Batchelor J (2019). Preservice student views of teacher judgement and practice in the age of artificial intelligence. *Southern African Review of Education*, 25(1), 70–88. <https://doi.org/10.10520/EJC-1877d530c6>
- Petticrew, M., & Roberts, H. (2006). *Systematic Reviews in the Social Sciences*. Blackwell Publishing.
- * Poitras, E., Mayne, Z., Huang, L., Udy, L., & Lajoie, S. (2019). Scaffolding student teachers' information-seeking behaviours with a network-based tutoring system. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 35(6), 731–746. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12380>

- Priem, J., Piwowar, H., & Orr, R. (2022). *OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.01833>
- * Rizqa, K., Drajadi, N. A., & Putra, K. A. (2022). Cognitive conflicts emerged from feedback from peer assessment and Artificial Intelligence. *Al-Hayat: Journal of Islamic Education*, 6(2), 391-403. <https://doi.org/10.35723/ajie.v6i2.256>
- * Rosanda, V., & Istenič, A. (2021). A Stranger in the classroom: Pre-service teachers' anxiety and negative attitudes toward humanoid social robots. In M. Rauterberg (Ed.), *Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Culture and Computing. Design Thinking and Cultural Computing* (Vol. 12795, pp. 461–473). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-77431-8_29
- Rudolph, J., Tan, S., & Tan, S. (2023). ChatGPT: Bullshit spewer or the end of traditional assessments in higher education?. *Journal of Applied Learning and Teaching*, 6(1), 342-363.
- * Ruwe, T., & Mayweg-Paus, E. (2023). “Your argumentation is good”, says the AI vs humans—The role of feedback providers and personalised language for feedback effectiveness. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 5, 100189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2023.100189>
- Saghiri, M. A., Vakhnovetsky, J., & Nadershahi, N. (2022). Scoping review of artificial intelligence and immersive digital tools in dental education. *Journal of Dental Education*, 86(6), 736–750. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jdd.12856>
- * Sailer, M., Bauer, E., Hofmann, R., Kiesewetter, J., Glas, J., Gurevych, I., & Fischer, F. (2023). Adaptive feedback from artificial neural networks facilitates pre-service teachers' diagnostic reasoning in simulation-based learning. *Learning and Instruction*, 83, 101620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2022.101620>
- Salas-Pilco, S. Z., Xiao, K., & Hu, X. (2022). Artificial intelligence and learning analytics in teacher education: A systematic review. *Education Sciences*, 12(8), 569.
- * Schmid, M., Brianza, E., & Petko, D. (2021). Self-reported technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) of pre-service teachers in relation to digital technology use in lesson plans. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 115, 106586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106586>
- * Schussler, D., Frank, J., Lee, T.K. & Mahfouz, J. (2017). Using virtual role-play to enhance teacher candidates' skills in responding to bullying. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 25(1), 91-120. Waynesville, NC USA: Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education. <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/173571/>.
- Shaik, T., Tao, X., Li, Y., Dann, C., McDonald, J., Redmond, P., & Galligan, L. (2022). A review of the trends and challenges in adopting natural language processing methods for education feedback analysis. *IEEE Access*, 10, 56720-56739.
- Sihare, S. R. (2024). Student dropout analysis in higher education and retention by artificial intelligence and machine learning. *SN Computer Science*, 5(2), 202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-023-02458-w>
- * Siiman, L. A. (2024). AI in teacher education: An introductory training session for pre-service teachers involving Microsoft Copilot. In Y.-P. Cheng, M. Pedaste, E. Bardone, & Y.-M. Huang (Eds.), *Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Innovative Technologies and Learning* (Vol. 14786, pp. 231–236). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65884-6_24
- Simsoft (2023). *SimInClass*. <https://simsoft.com.tr/en/our-solutions/gaming---simulation/siminclass>
- * Singh, H. P., & Alhulail, H. N. (2022). Predicting student-teachers dropout risk and early identification: A four-step logistic regression approach. *IEEE Access*, 10, 6470–6482. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3141992>
- * Slotte, A., Wallinheimo, K., Fors, U., Hägglund, S., & Selander, S. (2023). On the threshold of future learning. *Nordic Journal of Digital Literacy*, 18(2), 85–99. <https://doi.org/10.18261/njdl.18.2.2>
- * Smith, K. (2018). Perceptions of preservice teachers about adaptive learning programs in K-8 mathematics education. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 9(2), 111–130. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cet.414780>
- * Song, D., Oh, E. Y., & Hong, H. (2022). The impact of teaching simulation using student chatbots with different attitudes on preservice teachers' efficacy. *Educational Technology & Society*, 25(3), 46-59.
- * Stott, A., & Hattingh, A. (2015). Conceptual tutoring software for promoting deep learning: A case study. *Educational Technology & Society*, 18(2), 179–194.

- * Sun, F., Tian, P., Sun, D., Fan, Y., & Yang, Y. (2024). Pre-service teachers' inclination to integrate AI into STEM education: Analysis of influencing factors. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 00, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13469>
- Thomas, J., Graziosi, S., Brunton, J., Ghouze, Z., O'Driscoll, P., Bond, M., & Koryakina, A. (2023). *EPPI Reviewer: Advanced software for systematic reviews, maps and evidence synthesis* [Computer software]. EPPI Centre Software. UCL Social Research Institute. <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/cms/Default.aspx?alias=eppi.ioe.ac.uk/cms/er4>
- * Tirado-Olivares, S., Navío-Inglés, M., O'Connor-Jiménez, P., & Cózar-Gutiérrez, R. (2023). From human to machine: Investigating the effectiveness of the conversational AI ChatGPT in historical thinking. *Education Sciences*, 13(8), 803. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13080803>
- * Tunjera, N., & Chigona, A. (2023, October 26–27). *Investigating effective ways to use artificial intelligence in teacher education* [Conference paper]. 22nd European Conference on E-Learning (ECEL 2023), University of South Africa, South Africa. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecel.22.1.1625>
- * Tural, A., & Koçak, N. (2023). Awareness levels of social studies pre-service teachers regarding metaverse use. *Advanced Education*, 11(23), 69–86. <https://doi.org/10.20535/2410-8286.284683>
- UNESCO. (2022). *Transforming education from within: current trends in the status and development of teachers; World Teachers' Day 2022*. UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000383002>
- UNESCO. (2024a). *AI competency framework for students*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54675/JKJB9835>
- UNESCO. (2024b). *AI competency framework for teachers*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54675/ZJTE2084>
- U.S. Department of Education (2023). *Artificial Intelligence and the future of teaching and learning: Insights and recommendations*. Office of Educational Technology. <https://www2.ed.gov/documents/ai-report/ai-report.pdf>
- * Uzumcu, O., & Acilmis, H. (2024). Do innovative teachers use AI-powered tools more interactively? A study in the context of diffusion of innovation theory. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 29(2), 1109–1128. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-023-09687-1>
- * Vartiainen, H., & Tedre, M. (2023). Using artificial intelligence in craft education: Crafting with text-to-image generative models. *Digital Creativity*, 34(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14626268.2023.2174557>
- Vashishth, T. K., Sharma, V., Sharma, K. K., Kumar, B., Panwar, R., & Chaudhary, S. (2024). AI-driven learning analytics for personalized feedback and assessment in higher education. In *Using traditional design methods to enhance AI-driven decision making* (pp. 206-230). IGI Global.
- * Wang, D., Bian, C., & Chen, G. (2024). Using explainable AI to unravel classroom dialogue analysis: Effects of explanations on teachers' trust, technology acceptance and cognitive load. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, (55)6, 2530–2556. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13466>
- Warburton, S. (2009). Second Life in higher education: Assessing the potential for and the barriers to deploying virtual worlds in learning and teaching. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 40(3), 414–426. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2009.00952.x>
- Wonder (2024). *Wonder App*. <https://wonder.app>
- * Wulff, P., Buschhüter, D., Westphal, A., Mientus, L., Nowak, A., & Borowski, A. (2022). Bridging the gap between qualitative and quantitative assessment in science education research with machine learning — A case for pretrained language models-based clustering. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 31(4), 490–513. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-022-09969-w>
- * Wulff, P., Mientus, L., Nowak, A., & Borowski, A. (2023a). Utilizing a pretrained language model (BERT) to classify preservice physics teachers' written reflections. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 33(3), 439–466. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-022-00290-6>
- * Wulff, P., Westphal, A., Mientus, L., Nowak, A., & Borowski, A. (2023b). Enhancing writing analytics in science education research with machine learning and natural language

-
- processing—Formative assessment of science and non-science preservice teachers' written reflections. *Frontiers in Education*, 7, Article 1061461. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.1061461>
- * Xu, P., Liu, J., Jones, N., Cohen, J., & Ai, W. (2024). The promises and pitfalls of using language models to measure instruction quality in education. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.02444*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2404.02444>
- * Yoo, J., Park, J., Ha, M., & Mae Lagmay Darang, C. (2024). Exploring pre-service teachers' cognitive processes and calibration with an unsupervised learning-based automated evaluation system. *Sage Open*, 14(3), Article 21582440241262864. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241262864>
- Zawacki-Richter, O., Kerres, M., Bedenlier, S., Bond, M., & Buntins, K. (Eds.). (2020). *Systematic Reviews in Educational Research*. Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-27602-7>
- Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V. I., Bond, M., & Gouverneur, F. (2019). Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators? *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0>
- * Zemljak, D., & Kerneža, M. (2024). Bridging the gap: Understanding teacher perspectives on humanoid robots in education. In M. Marinšek & M. Hmelak (Eds.), *Interdisciplinary Research in Teaching and Learning: New Perspectives and Approaches* (pp. 203–224). University of Maribor Press. <https://doi.org/10.18690/um.pef.2.2024.12>
- * Zhang, J., & Zhang, Z. (2024). AI in teacher education: Unlocking new dimensions in teaching support, inclusive learning, and digital literacy. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 40(4), 1871–1885. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12988>
- * Zhang, C., Hofmann, F., Plöbl, L., & Gläser-Zikuda, M. (2024). Classification of reflective writing: A comparative analysis with shallow machine learning and pre-trained language models. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-12720-0>
- * Zhang, C., Schießl, J., Plöbl, L., Hofmann, F., & Gläser-Zikuda, M. (2023). Evaluating reflective writing in pre-service teachers: The potential of a mixed-methods approach. *Education Sciences*, 13(12), 1213. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13121213>
- * Zhou, Y. (2024, June 25-27). *The impact of the artificial intelligence (AI) Art Generator in pre-service art teacher training* [Conference paper]. 2024 IEEE Conference on Artificial Intelligence (CAI), Marina Bay Sands, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CAI59869.2024.00250>